

Electronic Supplementary Material for

Effects of phylogenetic distance, niche overlap and habitat alteration on spatial co-occurrence patterns in Neotropical bats and birds

Authors: Anikó B. Tóth, John Alroy, S. Kathleen Lyons, Andrew P. Allen

2025

Proceedings B

DOI: 10.1098/rspb.2024.1679

S1. Data

Mist-netted abundance data for bats and birds, along with accompanying site metadata (geographic coordinates, habitat categorization), were downloaded from the Ecological Register (<http://ecoregister.org>) [47] on 7 June 2020 for all sites south of the Tropic of Cancer (23.44°N) in Central and South America. The disturbance status of each site was assigned based on the 'altered.habitat' field in the site metadata, which is empty if the site is intact and filled with a land use category if the site is altered. Altered sites included cropland, disturbed forest, fragment, pasture, plantation, secondary forest, inhabited area, and combined categories [72].

The raw data contained 143 sites for bats and 105 sites for birds, but only subsets of these sites (106 for the bats and 84 for the birds) were included in our analyses to control for differences in the spatial distributions of altered and intact sites (Fig. S1). In particular, the intact sites cover more area than the altered sites, and the geographic coverage of the latter is nested within that of the former. To control for these differences, we removed the intact sites covering areas that were not covered by altered sites using the following algorithm: (1) we measured the distance to the closest altered site for all intact sites and vice versa; (2) we found the altered site farthest from its closest intact site; (3) we removed all intact sites whose closest altered neighbours were farther than the distance in step 2. Note that this approach only works because the geographic coverages are nested; site types that are offset in space would require a different approach. The resulting dataset contained bat assemblage data for 196 species collected from

53 altered and 53 intact sites, and bird assemblage data for 1230 species from 42 altered and 42 intact sites (Fig. S1). We pruned 6 bat species and 34 bird species from these datasets for our analyses due to incomplete dietary-guild or phylogenetic distance data, as detailed below. The R codes used to prepare the final datasets and to undertake the analyses can be found on Dryad (see data availability statement).

Dietary guild data was also obtained from the Ecological Register, which uses primary literature for its guild assignments, supplemented with additional dietary information from Birds of the World [62].

Specifically, we ensured that all hummingbird species were tabulated as primarily nectarivores and secondarily invertivores [73]. We updated dietary-guild information for species with missing data, where possible, and we separated the existing invertivore guild into invertivores and aquatic invertivores, as the dietary niches of birds feeding on these two groups are usually quite distinct. Species classified as omnivores in the Register were cross-checked in Birds of the World and left as omnivores if they regularly utilize three or more dietary sources (e.g. seeds, fruit, insects), including cases where individuals of a species were recorded with strongly varying gut contents (e.g. 3 individuals with all fruit and seeds and 4 individuals with all arthropods), and cases where the relative frequency of feeding on three or more dietary sources was not known. Species with low certainty for dietary guild were dropped. The final datasets include the following dietary-guild categories: aquatic invertivore, carnivore, frugivore, granivore (birds only), invertivore, nectarivore, omnivore, piscivore, and sanguinivore (bats only). Dietary guilds consist of combinations of up to two major diet categories (e.g. nectarivore-invertivore, piscivore-carnivore), as noted in the main text.

Phylogenetic distances for bat and bird and bat species pairs were calculated using trees obtained from the Open Tree of Life (OTL) [48] using the R package *rotl* [50]. Taxonomic names obtained from the Ecological Register that were not matched in the OTL were checked for typos or misspellings and then matched to the GBIF backbone taxonomy. Names identified as synonyms were matched to the OTL via the recognized GBIF name. The remaining unmatched names were removed; these were either unknown ambiguous names or suspected species complexes.

S2. Species diversity, turnover and composition in altered and intact habitats

To assess differences in species diversity, turnover, and composition between altered and intact bat and bird faunas, we run a suite of classical community analyses using the R package *vegan* [56]. Estimating diversity of each site using three metrics – a corrected first-order jackknife (cJ1) [74], the canonical Chao1 [75], and Fisher’s alpha [76] – we find that diversity is generally similar in altered and intact sites (Fig. S2A), although Wilcoxon rank-sum tests indicate that median values for Fisher’s alpha are somewhat higher in intact than altered habitats for bats (4.32 vs 3.32, Table S1).

To examine differences in species turnover between the two habitat types, we apply multivariate dispersion tests [77], implemented using the *betadisper* function, to both abundance and occurrence data. Multivariate dispersion tests are evaluated using the Jaccard, Otsuka-Ochiai, and Cosine similarity metrics [78]. These analyses reveal no significant differences in species turnover between the two habitat types (Table S2).

We assess differences in species composition using canonical correspondence analysis [79], along with the permutational multivariate ANOVA [80], which is performed with the same similarity metrics listed above. We also visualise differences in species composition among sites by performing multidimensional scaling analyses on the Otsuka-Ochiai metrics (Fig. S2B). Canonical correspondence analyses and permutational multivariate ANOVA reveal differences in species composition between habitats for the birds (Table S2), but not the bats.

S3. Performance of the NHD parameter

To demonstrate the behaviour of the NHD, we calculate how the distribution of N_{AB} (the number of sites in which co-occurrence is observed) values varies when the underlying association ranges from strong repulsion to strong attraction (i.e., θ ranging from -2 to 2). For these demonstrations, we use occurrence values that span most species in our datasets (N_A and N_B ranging from 2 to 8). The total number of sites is set at 50, which is similar to the values for the bird and bat datasets we analysed. Aside from demonstrating that increases in θ correspond to higher probabilities of more frequent co-occurrences (Fig. 2), as we would expect from a reliable metric, two noteworthy observations arise from these calculations. First, if occurrences of the two species are low relative to the total number of sites ($N_A =$

$N_B = 2$), $N_{AB} = 0$ is the most likely outcome even when $\theta = 2$, which corresponds to over 7-fold higher odds of species B occurring at a site if species A is present (light blue line in left panel of Fig. 2). Second, as the numbers of sites occupied by the two species increases, the distribution of N_{AB} values exhibits a greater shift in mode with changes in θ : when $N_A = N_B = 2$, the mode for N_{AB} remains at 0 for all three θ values (-2, 0, 2), whereas when $N_A = N_B = 8$, the mode shifts from 0 (at $\theta = -2$) to 4 (at $\theta = 2$).

To understand how the NHD behaves in relation to θ , we take logarithms of both sides of Eq. 1a, and differentiate with respect to θ , yielding an expression for the score:

$$\frac{\partial \log f(N_{AB} | \theta)}{\partial \theta} = N_{AB} - P_1(\theta)/P_0(\theta) \quad \text{Eq. S1a}$$

where

$$P_k(\theta) = \sum_{n=\max(0, N_B - N_{(A)})}^{\min(N_A, N_B)} \binom{N_A}{n} \binom{N_{(A)}}{N_B - n} \exp(n\theta) n^k \quad \text{Eq. S1b}$$

and $P_1(\theta)/P_0(\theta)$ is the average number of co-occurrences for the NHD [44]. Given that the maximum likelihood for θ , $\hat{\theta}$, is achieved when $\partial \log f(N_{AB} | \theta) / \partial \theta = 0$, Eq. S1 implies that $\hat{\theta}$ corresponds to the NHD with a mean equal to the observed number of co-occurrences, N_{AB} . While there is no exact analytical expression for this mean, accurate approximations have been derived [81]. Because the mean of this distribution cannot be equal to its minimum or maximum value if there is more than one possible number of co-occurrences, the estimate of $\hat{\theta}$ inferred from a single observation is undefined whenever the observed number of co-occurring sites N_{AB} is equal to the minimum or maximum possible values. In particular, $\hat{\theta} = -\infty$ when a pair has no co-occurrences because this corresponds to the minimum ($= \max(0, N_B - N_{(A)})$), and $\hat{\theta} = \infty$ when one species is only found where the other is present because this corresponds to the maximum ($= \min(N_A, N_B)$). While this behaviour is desirable because it means that θ accurately represents co-occurrence observations that, by themselves, are biologically uninformative, it highlights an overarching difficulty of traditional co-occurrence analysis: namely, that such edge cases are extremely common in most empirical datasets. Here we avoid this issue by adopting a Bayesian mixed-

effects modelling approach. This approach yields finite θ estimates by assigning prior distributions to the model parameters (discussed below), and by partially pooling data across co-occurrence sets to obtain the θ estimates.

These analyses bring to the forefront a key question: how reliably can we estimate species association using occurrence data alone? Our capacity to infer θ from observations is fundamentally constrained by the Fisher Information, which is the variance of the score [82]. We can characterise how the Fisher information varies with θ , $I(\theta)$, by combining Eqs. 1 and S1:

$$I(\theta) = E \left[\left(\frac{\partial \log f(N_{AB} | \theta)}{\partial \theta} \right)^2 \mid \theta \right] =$$

$$\sum_{n=\max(0, N_B - N_{(A)})}^{\min(N_A, N_B)} f(n | \theta) \left(\frac{\partial \log f(N_{AB} | \theta)}{\partial \theta} \right)^2 = \frac{P_2(\theta)}{P_0(\theta)} - \left(\frac{P_1(\theta)}{P_0(\theta)} \right)^2 \quad \text{Eq. S2}$$

Equation S2 demonstrates that, when the NHD is parameterised using θ , the Fisher Information is $P_2(\theta)/P_0(\theta) - (P_1(\theta)/P_0(\theta))^2$, which is the variance of the NHD. Calculations performed using Eq. S2 demonstrate that, for the occurrences encompassing most of our data (i.e. N_A and $N_B \leq 16$), the Fisher Information generally peaks at positive θ values and increases with the species occurrences N_A and N_B (Fig. S3). Loosely speaking, these results indicate that θ can be estimated with greater precision when $\theta > 0$, and when species occurrences are higher, because the distribution of co-occurrence values, N_{AB} , changes more rapidly with changes in θ . Eventually, however, the Fisher Information declines as the numbers of occurrences for the two species approach the total number of sites (note the depressed yellow curve for $N_A = N_B = 40$ in Fig. S3) due to an increasing lower bound on the minimum number of co-occurrences ($= \max(0, N_B - N_{(A)})$). The Fisher Information also approaches 0 for very low and very high values of θ , regardless of N_A and N_B , because the distributions of N_{AB} values eventually become concentrated on this lower bound as θ declines, and on the upper bound ($= \min(N_A, N_B)$) as θ increases.

Coding the model

We coded the model using a custom distribution in the R package *brms*, which generates *Stan* code for fitting Bayesian models. (See https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/brms/vignettes/brms_customfamilies.html for an illustrative example on specifying custom families in *brms*.) We assume that the dependent variable, the number of co-occurrences, N_{AB} , adheres to the NHD (Eq.1). For this distribution, the probability of N_{AB} co-occurrences depends not only of θ , but also on the numbers of occurrences for the species pair (N_A, N_B), and the total number of sites ($=N_A + N_B$). These additional quantities are included in the *brms* formula by specifying the dependent variable on the left hand side of the tilde as “`sb | vint(occ1, occ2, N_site) + weights(N_sb)`”, where `sb` is the number of co-occurrences for species A and B, `vint()` is a *brms* function used to submit additional integer values for the dependent variable to a custom distribution, `occ1` and `occ2` are the occurrences for species A and B, and `N_site` is the total number of sites. Because each row in the data frame represents co-occurrence data for multiple species pairs, the number of pairs represented by each row, `N_sb`, is also submitted to the log likelihood calculations using the function `weights()`.

The *Stan* code used to specify the log likelihood function for the NHD is inserted into the *Stan* code generated by *brms* using the *brms* function command `stanvar(block = 'functions', ...)`. This *Stan* code is given below:

```
real nch_lpmf(int sb, real mu, data array[] int ii, data array[] real lp) {
  real log_p = lp[sb - ii[1] + 1] + mu*sb -
    log_sum_exp(to_vector(lp) + mu*to_vector(ii));
  return (is_inf(log_p) || is_nan(log_p)) ? negative_infinity() : log_p;
}
```

Stan requires that log likelihood functions have names ending in `_lpmf` and that the first argument be value(s) for the dependent variable (in this case, the number of co-occurrences `sb`). Since this code represents a custom distribution family in *brms*, the second argument, representing the fitted parameter of the custom distribution (in this case, the NHD parameter θ), must be named `mu`. This log likelihood

function takes as input a vector of all possible co-occurrence values, `ii`, from $\max(0, N_B - N_{(A)})$ to $\min(N_A, N_B)$ (Eq. 1), along with another vector of the same length as `ii`, `lp`, which corresponds to the logarithm of the number of permutations, $\binom{N_A}{n} \binom{N_{(A)}}{N_B - n}$ (Eq. 1), for each possible co-occurrence value n in `ii`. Given that the vectors `ii` and `lp` are identical for every species pair with the same values for `occ1`, `occ2`, and `N_site`, we pre-calculate `ii` and `lp` for every observed occupancy pairing in the `Stan` transformed data block, which reduces the time required to fit the model by more than an order of magnitude. We insert these calculations into the `Stan` code generated by `brms` using the `brms` function command `stanvar(block = 'tdata', ...)`.

We undertake model selection using the R package `loo` [52]. The `loo` diagnostics generated based on our initial log likelihood calculations indicate that the posterior distributions of our datasets are sensitive to the removal of individual observations (for another data example where this phenomenon is observed, see https://users.aalto.fi/~ave/modelselection/roaches.html#5_Poisson_model_with_varying_intercept_and_integrated_LOO). To get around this issue, and improve the accuracy of our inferences, we calculate the pointwise log likelihood values by integrating over the random effects, as recommended by Vehtari *et al.* [52]. We perform this integration using the `Stan` function `integrate_1d()`. Two issues with this function are noteworthy. First, use of `integrate_1d()` requires that `ii` that `lp` both be precalculated, which we do in the transformed data block as described above. Second, `integrate_1d()` is only capable of computing one-dimensional integrals, but some of the models we consider have two random effects (see Tables S4 and S6). However, in such models, we assume that both terms have random effects only on the intercept, and we assume that these random effects are independent and normally distributed with means of 0. We can therefore reduce the double integral to a single integral by noting that the sum of two independent, normally distributed random variables is also normally distributed with a mean equal to the sum of the two means (in this case 0) and a variance equal to the sum of the two variances.

We fit the `brms` models using the default priors for the parameters: the intercept was assigned a t-distribution prior with 3 d.f., a mean of 1, and a scale parameter of 2.5; standard deviations for the random effects were assigned half-t-distribution priors with 3 d.f. and scale parameters of 2.5; and fixed

effects (representing slopes and group means) were implicitly assigned improper uniform priors on the interval $[-\infty, \infty]$ because no prior distributions were specified for these parameters. In the parlance of Bayesian analysis [83], these prior distributions ranged from uninformative (for the fixed effects) to weakly informative.

Supplementary References:

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Supplementary Figures and Tables:

Figure S1. Maps of Neotropical bat and bird sites before (top) and after (bottom) biogeographic matching procedure, with altered sites represented in beige and intact sites represented in teal.

Figure S2. Results of the classical community analyses showing similarities and differences between altered and intact habitat types. (A) Species richness using three different richness metrics, Chao1, corrected first-order jackknife (cJ1) and Fisher's alpha (fa). (B) Results of species composition analyses using multidimensional scaling on abundance and binary data.

Figure S3. Effects of occupancy (N_A and N_B) on the Fisher information when co-occurrences of species are modelled using the NHD parameter θ (Eq. 1) as a measure of spatial aggregation. The Fisher information is calculated using Eq. S2, assuming a total of $N_A + N_{(A)} = 50$ sites.

Figure S4. Frequency distribution of θ values at the level of pairs for (A) bats and (B) birds.

Figure S5. Diagnostic residuals, $\sqrt{|\theta - \bar{\theta}|}$, for the full bat model plotted against natural-logarithm-transformed values for the numbers of sites occupied by the (A) rarer and (B) more abundant species in the co-occurrence set, and (C) the number of pairs in the co-occurrence set. Each point represents a transformed difference between the θ estimate for the co-occurrence set and the estimate calculated based only on fixed effects ($\bar{\theta}$). Loess curves (blue lines) are included for visualisation only.

Figure S6. Diagnostic residuals, $\sqrt{|\theta - \bar{\theta}|}$, for the full bird model plotted against natural-logarithm-transformed values for the numbers of sites occupied by the (A) rarer and (B) more abundant species in the co-occurrence set, and (C) the number of pairs in the co-occurrence set. Each point represents a transformed difference between the θ estimate for the co-occurrence set and the estimate calculated based only on fixed effects ($\bar{\theta}$). Loess curves (blue lines) are included for visualisation only.

Table S1. Results of two-tailed Wilcoxon rank-sum test statistics (W) comparing median species alpha diversity between altered and intact sites for birds and bats. Sample sizes after biogeographic correction were 53 each of altered and intact bat sites and 42 each altered and intact bird sites.

Diversity metric	Taxon	Median Diversity		W	P-value
		Altered	Intact		
Chao-1	bat	19.3	18.5	1,037	0.521
Chao-1	bird	46.7	52.5	827	0.628
first-order jackknife	bat	17.1	16.9	1,318	0.585
first-order jackknife	bird	46.7	52.5	827	0.628
Fisher's alpha	bat	3.32	4.32	970	0.006
Fisher's alpha	bird	13.5	16.0	848	0.766

Table S2. Results of site-to-site species turnover (beta dispersion) and composition analyses (adonis = Multivariate permutational ANOVA and cca = canonical correspondence analysis) comparing community patterns in altered and intact habitats, such that significant p-values signal a difference in composition between the two site types. F-statistic and *p*-values are displayed for bats and birds.

analysis	data	metric	bats		birds	
			<i>p</i> -value	F statistic	<i>p</i> -value	F statistic
beta dispersion	binary	Jaccard	0.2171	1.5418	0.2070	1.6178
beta dispersion	binary	Ochiai	0.1079	2.6298	0.2142	1.5668
beta dispersion	abundance	Jaccard	0.6294	0.2342	0.4993	0.4605
beta dispersion	abundance	Cosine similarity	0.5953	0.2839	0.9509	0.0038
adonis	binary	Jaccard	0.5730	0.9218	0.0448	1.2880
adonis	binary	Ochiai	0.7345	0.7447	0.0353	1.4922
adonis	abundance	Jaccard	0.2557	1.1143	0.0157	1.2390
adonis	abundance	Cosine similarity	0.4612	0.9274	0.0118	1.6108
cca	binary	NA	0.3270	1.1722	0.0480	1.1484
cca	binary	NA	0.3770	1.1722	0.0630	1.1484
cca	abundance	NA	0.5940	1.7538	0.0060	1.6988
cca	abundance	NA	0.6240	1.7538	0.0090	1.6988

Table S3. Parameter estimates (posterior means and associated standard errors), along with 95% credible intervals (CIs), for the full and restricted-pool (RP) models presented in the main text for bats and birds. Predictor variables include standardised phylogenetic distance (PhyloD), dietary-guild overlap (DietOvl; levels: low, medium, high), and habitat (Habitat; levels: altered, intact). For the fixed effects, the coefficient for PhyloD represents a slope and the other coefficients represent deviations from the θ values predicted by the intercepts at the reference levels (low for DietOvl, altered for Habitat). For the random effects, standard deviations are separately calculated for each level of the categorical variable. The randomisation results are summarised using the 50%, 2.5%, and 97.5% quantiles (Q) of the posterior mean values for each parameter. These results were obtained by fitting models with the same fixed- and random-effects structures to 100 randomised datasets (see Methods of the main text for details).

TAXON	MODEL	VARIABLE	EFFECT TYPE	ESTIMATE	EST. ERROR	L-95% CI	U-95% CI	RANDOMISATION RESULTS		
								50% Q	2.5% Q	97.5% Q
BAT	FULL	Intercept	fixed	0.408	0.026	0.357	0.459	0.429	0.395	0.471
BAT	FULL	PhyloD	fixed	-0.100	0.022	-0.143	-0.058	0.001	-0.035	0.035
BAT	FULL	DietOvlpmedium	fixed	0.349	0.066	0.218	0.476	0.007	-0.209	0.188
BAT	FULL	DietOvlphigh	fixed	0.005	0.059	-0.110	0.118	0.020	-0.077	0.109
BAT	FULL	sd(DietOvlplow)	random	0.604	0.028	0.551	0.658	0.184	0.097	0.248
BAT	FULL	sd(DietOvlpmedium)	random	0.524	0.091	0.342	0.705	0.216	0.101	0.439
BAT	FULL	sd(DietOvlphigh)	random	0.865	0.041	0.785	0.948	0.181	0.071	0.281
BAT	RP	Intercept	fixed	0.400	0.027	0.348	0.453	0.428	0.386	0.471
BAT	RP	PhyloD	fixed	-0.113	0.023	-0.159	-0.069	0.002	-0.028	0.042
BAT	RP	DietOvlpmedium	fixed	0.353	0.074	0.210	0.496	0.019	-0.217	0.186
BAT	RP	DietOvlphigh	fixed	-0.009	0.062	-0.128	0.114	0.001	-0.076	0.098
BAT	RP	sd(DietOvlplow)	random	0.622	0.030	0.564	0.682	0.164	0.063	0.272
BAT	RP	sd(DietOvlpmedium)	random	0.595	0.097	0.408	0.789	0.191	0.104	0.462
BAT	RP	sd(DietOvlphigh)	random	0.882	0.046	0.794	0.974	0.165	0.071	0.305
BIRD	FULL	Intercept	fixed	0.336	0.010	0.316	0.356	0.359	0.343	0.372
BIRD	FULL	PhyloD	fixed	-0.103	0.006	-0.115	-0.092	0.000	-0.007	0.012
BIRD	FULL	sd(Habitataltered)	random	0.604	0.016	0.573	0.634	0.150	0.094	0.208
BIRD	FULL	sd(Habitatintact)	random	0.623	0.015	0.594	0.653	0.118	0.086	0.155
BIRD	RP	Intercept	fixed	0.315	0.014	0.288	0.344	0.341	0.326	0.354

BIRD	RP	PhyloD	fixed	-0.096	0.007	-0.110	-0.082	0.002	-0.009	0.012
BIRD	RP	Habitatintact	fixed	0.055	0.020	0.016	0.094	0.083	0.064	0.101
BIRD	RP	sd(DietOvplow)	random	0.549	0.020	0.510	0.590	0.145	0.074	0.214
BIRD	RP	sd(DietOvlpmedium)	random	0.467	0.017	0.436	0.501	0.115	0.048	0.165
BIRD	RP	sd(DietOvphigh)	random	0.646	0.027	0.594	0.701	0.097	0.042	0.145

Table S4. Results of model selection for the best random-effects structure for the full bat model. Variables used to characterize random-effects structures included habitat (altered, intact), dietary-guild overlap (high, medium, low), diet pairing (e.g. invertivore-granivore), and occupancy pairing “OccPr” (e.g. {1,1}, {1,2}). Interactions among variables are denoted by colons. Random effects are specified using *brms* notation: “by = Constant” means that only one random-effects variance is estimated, while “by = Habitat” means that random-effects standard deviations are separately estimated for each type of habitat. Models have been ranked from best to worst based on the expected log predictive density (ELPD). Z-scores have been calculated based on the ELPD differences and associated standard errors between the model with the best random effects structure (re14) and the other models. The fixed-effects structure was held constant (fx01 in Table S5) for all comparisons.

id	random effects structure	ΔE	$S_{\Delta E}$	$Z_{\Delta E}$
re14	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	0.00	0.00	NA
re15	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	18.51	7.55	2.45
re13	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	18.75	7.44	2.52
re20	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	79.36	8.67	9.15
re21	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	89.83	10.14	8.86
re19	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	90.08	10.14	8.89
re18	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	117.41	11.05	10.63
re16	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	120.11	10.72	11.20
re17	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	128.55	9.06	14.19
re2	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	224.84	15.19	14.80
re8	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	233.10	15.47	15.06
re23	(1 gr(DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	238.32	15.42	15.46
re3	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	238.72	16.60	14.38
re7	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	240.89	16.92	14.24
re1	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	243.13	16.60	14.65
re24	(1 gr(DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	245.25	16.99	14.43
re9	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	246.94	17.28	14.29
re22	(1 gr(DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	248.13	16.76	14.81
re11	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	290.82	17.02	17.08
re12	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	303.40	17.69	17.16
re5	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+	303.89	17.05	17.82

	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))			
re4	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	309.75	17.54	17.66
re10	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	310.70	18.09	17.18
re6	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	312.30	17.59	17.75
re26	(1 gr(Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	346.75	21.73	15.96
re25	(1 gr(Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	356.56	21.74	16.40
re27	no random effect	654.21	33.95	19.27

Table S5. Results of model selection for the best fixed-effects structure for the full bat model. Candidate predictors included standardized phylogenetic distance (binned into 5 values), habitat (altered, intact), and dietary-guild overlap (high, medium, low). Interactions among variables are denoted by colons. Models have been ranked from best to worst based on the expected log predictive density (ELPD). Z-scores have been calculated based on the ELPD differences and associated standard errors between the top model and the other models. The random-effects structure was held constant (re14 in Table S4) for all comparisons. Grey highlighted rows are used to calculate $z_{\Delta E}$ values referred to in the main text.

id	fixed effects structure	ΔE	$S_{\Delta E}$	$z_{\Delta E}$
fx16	PhyloD + DietOvlp	0	0	NA
fx12	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat	0.931	1.750	0.532
fx11	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ PhyloD:DietOvlp	3.148	3.781	0.833
fx8	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:Habitat	3.329	2.111	1.577
fx10	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp	4.533	4.100	1.106
fx7	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp+ PhyloD:Habitat	6.374	4.241	1.503
fx5	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	7.840	3.823	2.051
fx3	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	8.930	3.964	2.253
fx4	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp+ DietOvlp:Habitat	9.870	5.433	1.817
fx2	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp+ PhyloD:Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	12.674	5.571	2.275
fx18	PhyloD	13.583	5.973	2.274
fx14	PhyloD + Habitat	15.719	6.327	2.484
fx1	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp + PhyloD:Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat	15.885	6.366	2.496
fx9	PhyloD + Habitat + PhyloD:Habitat	17.289	6.413	2.696
fx17	DietOvlp	28.009	7.003	3.999
fx13	DietOvlp+ Habitat	29.773	7.232	4.117
fx6	DietOvlp+ Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	36.380	8.004	4.545
fx19	intercept only	45.279	10.431	4.341

Table S6. Results of model selection for the best random-effects structure for the full bird model.

Variables used to characterize random-effects structures included habitat (altered, intact), dietary-guild overlap (high, medium, low), diet pairing (e.g. invertivore-granivore), and occupancy pairing “OccPr” (e.g. {1,1}, {1,2}). Interactions among variables are denoted by colons. Random effects are specified using *brms* notation: “by = Constant” means that only one random-effects variance is estimated, while “by = Habitat” means that random-effects variances are separately estimated for each type of habitat. Models have been ranked from best to worst based on the expected log predictive density (ELPD). Z-scores have been calculated based on the ELPD differences and associated standard errors between the model with the best random effects structure (re15) and the other models. The fixed-effects structure was held constant (fx01 in Table S7) for all comparisons.

rand_id	random effects structure	ΔE	$S_{\Delta E}$	$Z_{\Delta E}$
re15	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	0.000	0.000	NA
re14	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	14.645	6.752	2.169
re13	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	51.660	3.832	13.480
re21	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	565.873	18.194	31.103
re19	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	688.675	19.291	35.700
re20	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	945.380	24.770	38.167
re18	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	2302.804	32.949	69.890
re16	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	2319.959	31.139	74.504
re17	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	2337.114	33.316	70.149
re24	(1 gr(DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	3082.149	45.025	68.455
re22	(1 gr(DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	3127.622	42.874	72.950
re23	(1 gr(DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	3129.353	43.256	72.346
re26	(1 gr(Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	3573.385	50.671	70.521
re25	(1 gr(Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	3576.195	48.825	73.245
re1	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	3740.656	68.104	54.925
re2	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	3792.615	69.330	54.704
re3	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	3862.297	70.176	55.037
re27	no random effect	4090.432	74.113	55.192

re4	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	4239.804	67.656	62.667
re6	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	4365.846	70.273	62.127
re5	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	4486.786	68.204	65.785
re7	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	5536.293	91.364	60.596
re10	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	5589.304	86.261	64.795
re8	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	5653.364	93.196	60.661
re9	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	5861.427	95.239	61.544
re11	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	6270.405	89.787	69.837
re12	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	6279.098	94.459	66.475

Table S7. Results of model selection for the best fixed-effects structure for the full bird model. Candidate predictors included standardized phylogenetic distance (binned into 5 values), habitat (altered, intact), and dietary-guild overlap (high, medium, low). Interactions among variables are denoted by colons. Models have been ranked from best to worst based on the expected log predictive density (ELPD). Z-scores have been calculated based on the ELPD differences and associated standard errors between the top model and the other models. The random-effects structure was held constant (re15 in Table S6) for all comparisons. Grey highlighted rows are used to calculate $z_{\Delta E}$ values referred to in the main text.

fixed_id	fixed effects structure	ΔE	$S_{\Delta E}$	$z_{\Delta E}$
fx18	PhyloD	0	0	NA
fx14	PhyloD + Habitat	37.507	19.190	1.955
fx9	PhyloD + Habitat + PhyloD:Habitat	60.665	20.770	2.921
fx11	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ PhyloD:DietOvlp	86.168	12.254	7.032
fx10	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp	93.151	21.993	4.236
fx4	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp+ DietOvlp:Habitat	98.550	23.752	4.149
fx2	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp+ PhyloD:Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	109.139	23.593	4.626
fx7	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp+ PhyloD:Habitat	118.475	23.306	5.083
fx1	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp + PhyloD:Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat	152.876	26.161	5.844
fx16	PhyloD + DietOvlp	234.678	14.858	15.794
fx12	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat	246.992	23.021	10.729
fx5	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	264.327	25.383	10.413
fx3	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	269.289	25.258	10.661
fx8	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:Habitat	275.894	24.263	11.371
fx15	Habitat	1068.191	42.309	25.247
fx19	intercept only	1123.674	40.913	27.465
fx13	DietOvlp+ Habitat	1643.247	51.712	31.777
fx6	DietOvlp+ Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	1707.285	53.651	31.822

Table S8. Results of model selection for the best random-effects structure for the restricted-pool bat model. Variables used to characterize random-effects structures included habitat (altered, intact), dietary-guild overlap (high, medium, low), diet pairing (e.g. invertivore-granivore), and occupancy pairing “OccPr” (e.g. {1,1}, {1,2}). Interactions among variables are denoted by colons. Random effects are specified using *brms* notation: “by = Constant” means that only one random-effects variance is estimated, while “by = Habitat” means that random-effects variances are separately estimated for each type of habitat. Models have been ranked from best to worst based on the expected log predictive density (ELPD). Z-scores have been calculated based on the ELPD differences and associated standard errors between the model with the best random effects structure (re14) and the other models. The fixed-effects structure was held constant (fx01 in Table S9) for all comparisons.

id	random effects structure	ΔE	$S_{\Delta E}$	$Z_{\Delta E}$
re14	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	0	0	NA
re13	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	12.704	6.517	1.949
re15	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	13.339	6.566	2.032
re20	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	76.558	8.384	9.132
re19	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	78.486	8.795	8.924
re21	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	79.862	8.842	9.032
re18	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	106.795	10.146	10.526
re16	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	108.233	9.887	10.947
re17	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	116.627	8.654	13.476
re8	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	145.576	11.916	12.217
re2	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	149.298	11.854	12.594
re7	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	159.289	13.676	11.648
re9	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	162.780	13.736	11.850
re1	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	166.019	13.551	12.251
re3	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	169.394	13.543	12.508
re11	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	219.684	14.307	15.355
re10	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	223.431	14.711	15.188
re23	(1 gr(DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	224.700	15.302	14.685

re12	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	225.206	14.716	15.304
re24	(1 gr(DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	225.452	16.135	13.973
re22	(1 gr(DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	227.307	16.036	14.174
re5	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	231.214	14.520	15.923
re6	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	232.483	14.641	15.878
re4	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	233.330	14.649	15.928
re26	(1 gr(Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	324.922	21.162	15.354
re25	(1 gr(Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	333.824	21.369	15.622
re27	no random effect	574.009	32.625	17.594

Table S9. Results of model selection for the best fixed-effects structure for the restricted-pool bat model. Candidate predictors included standardized phylogenetic distance (binned into 5 values), habitat (altered, intact), and dietary-guild overlap (high, medium, low). Interactions among variables are denoted by colons. Models have been ranked from best to worst based on the expected log predictive density (ELPD). Z-scores have been calculated based on the ELPD differences and associated standard errors between the top model and the other models. The random-effects structure was held constant (re14 in Table S8) for all comparisons. Grey highlighted rows are used to calculate $z_{\Delta E}$ values referred to in the main text.

id	fixed effects structure	ΔE	$S_{\Delta E}$	$z_{\Delta E}$
fx16	PhyloD + DietOvlp	0.000	0.000	NA
fx12	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat	0.679	1.918	0.354
fx10	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp	1.390	3.766	0.369
fx11	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ PhyloD:DietOvlp	1.407	3.253	0.432
fx8	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:Habitat	1.871	2.587	0.723
fx5	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	2.434	4.069	0.598
fx7	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp+ PhyloD:Habitat	2.772	4.086	0.679
fx4	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp+ DietOvlp:Habitat	4.201	5.170	0.813
fx3	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	4.527	4.093	1.106
fx2	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp+ PhyloD:Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	5.422	5.211	1.040
fx1	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp + PhyloD:Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat	7.046	5.781	1.219
fx18	PhyloD	12.347	5.351	2.308
fx14	PhyloD + Habitat	12.577	5.741	2.191
fx9	PhyloD + Habitat + PhyloD:Habitat	14.085	6.008	2.344
fx17	DietOvlp	20.176	6.758	2.985
fx13	DietOvlp+ Habitat	21.196	6.975	3.039
fx6	DietOvlp+ Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	23.753	7.790	3.049
fx19	intercept only	35.576	9.777	3.639

Table S10. Results of model selection for the best random-effects structure for the restricted-pool bird model. Variables used to characterize random-effects structures included habitat (altered, intact), dietary-guild overlap (high, medium, low), diet pairing (e.g. invertivore-granivore), and occupancy pairing “OccPr” (e.g. {1,1}, {1,2}). Interactions among variables are denoted by colons. Random effects are specified using *brms* notation: “by = Constant” means that only one random-effects variance is estimated, while “by = Habitat” means that random-effects variances are separately estimated for each type of habitat. Models have been ranked from best to worst based on the expected log predictive density (ELPD). Z-scores have been calculated based on the ELPD differences and associated standard errors between the model with the best random effects structure (re14) and the other models. The fixed-effects structure was held constant (fx01 in Table S11) for all comparisons.

rand_id	random effects structure	ΔE	$S_{\Delta E}$	$Z_{\Delta E}$
re14	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	0	0	NA
re8	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	69.761	12.544	5.561
re2	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	82.606	9.123	9.055
re13	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	98.226	9.533	10.303
re15	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	107.051	9.789	10.936
re9	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	149.002	14.727	10.117
re7	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	153.598	14.731	10.427
re1	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	168.943	13.205	12.794
re3	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	187.047	14.393	12.995
re10	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	719.635	19.105	37.668
re12	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	723.017	19.024	38.005
re21	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	745.196	23.028	32.361
re19	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	759.696	23.333	32.558
re4	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	790.310	22.887	34.531
re6	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	794.578	23.307	34.092
re11	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair,by=Constant))	825.180	19.941	41.381
re20	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	882.439	26.057	33.865
re5	(1 gr(DietPair:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))+ (1 gr(DietPair:Habitat,by=Constant))	892.044	24.590	36.277

re16	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	1091.050	18.276	59.697
re17	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	1094.274	15.937	68.663
re18	(1 gr(PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	1119.136	18.419	60.760
re24	(1 gr(DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	1774.962	28.203	62.935
re22	(1 gr(DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	1783.027	28.271	63.069
re23	(1 gr(DietOvlp:Habitat:OccPair,by=DietOvlp))	1789.860	28.278	63.295
re25	(1 gr(Habitat:OccPair,by=Constant))	2070.505	31.417	65.904
re26	(1 gr(Habitat:OccPair,by=Habitat))	2072.169	31.369	66.058
re27	no random effect	2711.490	49.302	54.998

Table S11. Results of model selection for the best fixed-effects structure for the restricted-pool bird model. Candidate predictors included standardized phylogenetic distance (binned into 5 values), habitat (altered, intact), and dietary-guild overlap (high, medium, low). Interactions among variables are denoted by colons. Models have been ranked from best to worst based on the expected log predictive density (ELPD). Z-scores have been calculated based on the ELPD differences and associated standard errors between the top model and the other models. The random-effects structure was held constant (re14 in Table S10) for all comparisons. Grey highlighted rows are used to calculate $z_{\Delta E}$ values referred to in the main text.

id	fixed effects structure	ΔE	$S_{\Delta E}$	$z_{\Delta E}$
fx14	PhyloD + Habitat	0.000	0.000	NA
fx9	PhyloD + Habitat + PhyloD:Habitat	4.601	1.415	3.251
fx18	PhyloD	6.912	6.583	1.050
fx10	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp	35.548	8.862	4.011
fx7	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp+ PhyloD:Habitat	39.114	8.872	4.409
fx11	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ PhyloD:DietOvlp	39.528	10.885	3.631
fx4	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp+ DietOvlp:Habitat	48.900	10.313	4.742
fx2	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp+ PhyloD:Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	51.863	10.988	4.720
fx8	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:Habitat	54.568	8.016	6.808
fx12	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat	56.150	7.789	7.209
fx16	PhyloD + DietOvlp	60.987	10.227	5.964
fx5	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	67.130	9.424	7.123
fx1	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp + PhyloD:Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat + PhyloD:DietOvlp:Habitat	68.001	13.275	5.123
fx3	PhyloD + DietOvlp+ Habitat + PhyloD:Habitat + DietOvlp:Habitat	73.662	10.293	7.156
fx15	Habitat	98.784	25.365	3.894
fx19	intercept only	100.837	25.996	3.879
fx13	DietOvlp+ Habitat	339.569	31.806	10.676
fx17	DietOvlp	341.618	32.258	10.590